

four replications to evaluate four varieties or lines at five rainfed lowland sites. Seeding rate was 60 kg/ha; plant spacing was 30 cm between rows. N, P, and K were applied at 200, 39, and 52 kg/ha, respectively. Integrated pest management was practiced. The field was hand-weeded 3 and 7 wk after planting.

Line BR319-1-HR38 and variety IR74 had continuous good performances for gogoranch cultural practices in the rainfed area of South Sulawesi. BR319-1-HR38 was released as Cenranae in Mar 1991 by the Indonesian Ministry of Agriculture.

Table 2. Agronomic traits and physiological character of Cenranae (BR319-1-HR38) and IR74. MORIF, 1991.

Variety or line	Maturity (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles (no./hill)	1,000-grain wt (g)	Reaction ^a to brown planthopper biotypes			Blast	Bacterial blight	Rice tungro disease
					1	2	3			
Cenranae ^a	112	120	11	30	R	MS	S	R	R	R
IR74	110	95	16	25	R	R	R	R	MR	R

^a R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible.

Cenranae yielded 20-44% more than the best regional check, Cisokan, and 21-55% more than another check, Cikapundung, in several trials (Table 1).

Cenranae is medium tall, has a medium number of tillers/hill, and high 1,000-grain

weight. Cenranae only resists BPH biotype 1 (Table 2). Both Cenranae and IR74 are suggested as gogoranch varieties for rainfed conditions in dry climates. □

CSR10, a newly released dwarf rice for salt-affected soils

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CSR10 is a short-duration (120-125 d) salt-tolerant rice variety developed for cultivation in saline soils. It combines salt tolerance and dwarfism from M40-431-24-114 (F₁ mutant of CSR1/IR8) and high-yielding ability from Jaya.

It was released by Central Variety Release Committee for sodic and saline soils in India. This variety can tolerate sodicity stress up to pH 10.2, exchangeable sodium percentage 73 without soil amendment, and salinity up to ECe 10 dS/m.

CSR10 is dwarf (80-85 cm) with compact plant type. It has a strong culm, photoperiod insensitivity, fertilizer responsiveness, and grain yield potential of 5-6 t/ha in nonstressed (normal) soils and 3-4.5 t/ha in highly deteriorated salt-affected soils. The short, bold kernels have acceptable cooking and eating quality. It is a white rice with high amylose content.

CSR10 yielded 2.7-5.7 t grain/ha compared with 1.9-4.9 t/ha for various checks in several trials (see table). No soil amendments were applied in the trials.

Marginal farmers can grow this variety as a biological amendment to enhance barren land productivity. Cultivation of CSR10 for three consecutive seasons improves soil and reduces sodicity stress. □

Performance of salt-tolerant rice variety CSR10 in different trials.

Trials	Av grain yield (t/ha)		Increase (%) over check	Trials	Av grain yield (t/ha)		Increase (%) over check
	CSR10	Check			CSR10	Check	
Breeding station (moderate stress)	5.7	4.9 (CSR1)	15.8	Minikit trials (sodic, saline, and saline-sodic environments)	3.8	2.6 (Jaya)	46.1
National Saline Alkaline Tolerant Varietal Trial 1986 and 1987 (sodic and saline environments)	3.1	2.7 (Pokkali)	14.8	Adaptive trials (saline-sodic environment)	2.7	1.9 (Saket 4)	42.1

Five lowland rice cultivars released in Turkey

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TARI developed and released lowland cultivars Altinyazi, Trakya, Meric, Ipsala,

and Ergene in Turkey in 1990. Turkish consumers prefer Ipsala and Meric because of their high grain quality. Ergene is an early variety. Altinyazi is a cold-tolerant variety.

Some agronomic and quality characteristics of these cultivars are given in Tables 1 and 2. □

Table 1. Some agronomic characteristics of newly released rice cultivars.

Variety	Pedigree (cross)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Plant height (cm)	Days to maturity (d)	Panicle length (cm)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	Sterility (%)
Altinyazi	TR-6 (Baldo/Ribel)	7.5	112	127	18.6	110	10.1
Trakya	TR-13 (Baldo/Komsomolsky)	8.5	113	128	18.1	122	24.6
Ergene	TR-19 (Delta/Zoria)	7.0	100	117	17.4	95	11.8
Meric	TR-22 (Delta/Akceltik)	8.0	100	125	17.9	101	14.6
Ipsala	TR-81 (Rodina/Delta)	8.2	110	125	20.1	110	21.8

Table 2. Some grain quality characteristics of newly released rice cultivars.

Variety	Brown rice		1000-grain weight (g)	Appearance of polished rice
	Length (mm)	Breadth (mm)		
Altinyazi	7.2	2.3	36	Translucent with white belly
Trakya	6.9	3.2	38	Translucent
Ergene	7.4	2.9	37	Translucent
Meric	7.3	2.3	38	Translucent
Ipsala	7.8	3.1	40	Translucent